

Shivapura Dhwaja Satyagraha: The 1st Session of Mysore Congress a Revisit

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Introduction

Before Independence Kannada speaking, people were classified into many administrative units. There were nearly 22 different administrations or states within the present Karnataka. Some parts of Karnataka were direct ruled by British which was generally called as British Karnataka, and some were Princely states which were ordered by the native rulers, they were named as parts of Indian India This kind of two administrations naturally created a kind confusion in the mind of freedom fighters.

Mysore, then a princely state was ruled by Wodeyar dynasty, who were the ex-rulers of Mysore overtaken by Hyder Ali and his son Tippu Sultan who ruled the region from Srirangapatna until 1799. Tippu had taken the help of French, Arch rivals of British, in building a strong army. This was not liked by the British, and they saw a potential threat to their sovereignty. They conspired with Marathas and Nizam of Hyderabad in facing Tippu and bringing his comedown. Thus gained a stronghold on entire south. Thus the region ruled by Tippu was divided into the allies and became part of Maratha,(Bombay Karnataka) Nizam (Hyderabad Karnataka) and Madras presidency (British Karnataka) region. The original Mysore state was handed over to Wodeyar dynasty, and KrishnarajaWodeyar III became the Maharaja of Mysore. A New era began in the history of Mysore. After that, the political changes had a significant impact on the development of Mysore. The Nagar revolution of 1831, as a result, the direct rule of British in the Mysore was imposed. For another half a century Mysore was ruled by the Commissioners. Later in 1881, the rendition of Mysore took place. As a result, the powers were handed over to Chamaraja wodeyar X. Krishnaraja Wodeyar IV succeeded him. Both the Maharajas were blessed with eminent Dewans like Rangacharlu, K.,Sheshadri Iyer, Sir M.Vishveshwaraiah. And Sir Mirza Ismail.

Wodeyars enjoyed support with the people because of their love, forward-looking administration, and Mysore was at the forefront of development. They had introduced in 1881, Mysore Representative Assembly a representational house to discuss the improvement status

of the state for the first time in India. They had built a dam across river Cauvery to improve irrigation facility, Asia's first power generation came up, and power was transferred to Kolar Goldfields(KGF) which were a remarkable unheard feat in the world at that time.

This interaction and involvement seeped well, though the rulers were affectionately adored, they were seen as puppets of British and an urge for self-rule under the auspicious of Maharaja or otherwise was wished by various leaders. So the Mysore State Congress came up with the leadership of M.Venkatakrishnaiah The Grand Old Man of Mysore who was popularly known as Tatayya. H.K.Veeranna Gowda, B.N.Gupta, K.T.Bhashyam, M.N.Jois, Subbamma Jois, S. Nijalingappa, Parthanyana Pandit, T.Siddalingaiah, and a host of others. Social meetings like Khadi, Gram Swaraj of Gandhi increased popularity. The top leadership of Congress did not like to agonize the princely states as they were sympathetic to the Indian struggle movement. Mahatma Gandhi, Sardar Vallabha Bhai Pater, Jawaharlal Nehru, and other national leaders were well received in Mysore whenever Mahatma Gandhi paid a visit. He was aware of the developmental work carried out in the state. He called Mysore as a Model State, and Maharaja Krishna Raja Wodeyar as Rajarishi Maharaja of Mysore was seen as a supporter of self-rule, already the state had introduced the Mysore Representative Assembly thought it was an organization of elite members of society. Those who already had the advantage of rendering in these Assembly wanted more say in the day-to-day administration and representations were being sent regularly.

During the plenary session of Indian National Congress held at Belgaum in 1924 where Mahatma Gandhi presided over the meeting, the call of recognition of Congress of princely states was granted by All India Congress Committee. They were permitted to use the Congress flag. Initially, Gandhi did not allow of this measure and wanted that each state Congress has its own so that it can be seen as a single unit.

They were handy in organizing the quiet conduct of Congress plenary session at Kakinada in 1923 and gained the recognition of topmost leadership. Dr. N.S. Hardikar took the initiative to bring up such volunteers throughout India under the auspicious of Hindustan Sevalal in 1924. This unit played a pivotal role in the ahimsa model of Indian Independence conflict after that. The youth volunteers from the Mysore region played a leading role in establishing Sevalal throughout India as they had been already trained. They played a pivotal role in the Satyagraha movement in British India.

Following recall of Non-Cooperation movement by Mr. Gandhi owing to violence in 1922, the leadership of Congress was worried, Dr. N.S.Hardikar, Congress leader from Hubli came-up with a band of volunteers who were well trained in the principles of Satyagraha. They used to lead camps to train these men in self-help, man management, faith in leadership, will to tolerate punishment from the British, etc. The call from Dr. Hardikar for 400-500 volunteers was taken sincerely by Mysore state youths, and they joined in hundreds and National College, Bangalore became the hub of activity.

British had a representative in the state as IGP, who had law and order in his jurisdiction. This was viewed by common people as background interference by the British. They could enforce their command easily on the princely states rather than in places controlled by them. One such instance was not to fly any another flag except state flag, at that point lifting flag was not given prominence or patriotic symbol, and it was not an issue at all.

Gandhi-Irwin pact in 1931 paved the way for elections to the provincial council, and many had the opportunity to participate in Government. Neighboring Madras province also had the votes, and Mr.Rajgopalachari took over as the Minister of the region. This created an uneasy situation in already disgruntled members of Representative Assembly in Mysore. They made a political entity

called Praja Paksha. The pressure mounted on the ruler and an election were called for. Mysore Congress also jumped into the fray. Talks with both parties under the auspicious of Shree. B.N. Gupta paved the way for a merger of the two as both had the same issue of forming a representative Government to the state. Thus by the time the elections were ended, both parties merged under the leadership of K.T. Bhashyam Iyengar.

The first conference of Mysuru Congress was conducted in 1938 at Shivapura. After this struggle, the movement for independence became stronger. H. K. Veerannagowda, a Veteran Congress leader, opined that Shivapura on the highway was most suitable for the great event. The leaders of those days like Sahukar Chennaiah, H. C. Dasappa, Rangarajan, M.N. Jois, and others took the lead. Each one was allotted separate duties, including food arrangements. T. Siddlingaiah was elected as the president of the Committee of Satyagraha. Many villagers showed their solidarity by contributing money. A place which can hold about 40,000 people was selected.

The plenary session was summoned at Shivapura on Mysore- Bangalore Highway. As that was a post-harvest season, the paddy fields were empty, and a considerable ground was readied for the session. The arrangements were meticulously planned by a committee headed by S chukar Chennaiah. The talk of Satyagraha had created a charged atmosphere; it was also helped by the recent agitation of ryots of the region. The arrangements were made for 50,000 people to attend. There were special trains arranged from both Mysore and Bangalore directions so that people could participate. The session took off with a lot of fanfare and the president of the course T.Siddalingaiah was taken on a long procession around lakh people gather on occasion. The second day was to have flag hoisting as its first items and then the main agenda. The IGP had taken objection to the event as it was banned and conveyed the same to District administration to prevent the same. DC Shri.M ekhri had taken a stand that he would not take action unless there are law and order problem and issued strict orders to Superintendent of Police to oversee the event. The atmosphere was charged, the flag post was well guarded by 25-30 women members of Congress, guarding them were the Sevadal volunteers and the huge crowd was in the outer ring guarded in between by Sevadal volunteers.

Sevadal J.O.C., .M.N. Jois called the president to hoist the flag, as soon as he touched the flag the police intervened and arrested stating he had violated the rule. Volunteers managed the situation with a cry of Jindabad !! and in the meanwhile .M.N.Jois who was beside the arrested president hoisted the flag on his behalf. Thus the planned event was accomplished even under the nose of the British police force. Several arrests were made, even then the flag post was guarded by the charged mob throughout the day, and the news spread like wildfire throughout the State. The success was seen as an excellent example of non-violence satyagraha marking the entry of princely states into the Indian Independence struggle.

Conclusion

A great history was made on 26th April 1938 at Shivapur, 7 Kms from Maddur., taluk headquarters of Mandya district. 600 Policemen with open Gun were facing the nearly 40,000 healthy crowds in a free space of 14-15 acre of paddy field. Anything could have happened a wrong move could have sparked the situation. But the well-trained ahimsa crowd saw the victory of Gandhiji's principle. Some arrests of the leaders were the action that the police could do on that day. But the first Session of Mysore Congress created a new History in the annals of the freedom movement of Mysore as we the Karnataka.

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